

Research Article

Teachers Attitude and Students' Achievement in Selected Private Secondary Schools in Rubavu District, Rwanda

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Article History	Abstract
<p>Received: January 25, 2026 Accepted: February 17, 2026 Published: February 24, 2026</p>	<p>This study examines Teachers' Attitudes and Students' Achievement in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District, Rwanda. The main objective was to find out if there is any relationship between teachers' attitude and students' achievement in selected private secondary schools. The study used the descriptive survey method design, and data were analyzed using the mean and Pearson's correlation coefficient. The total sampling technique was used whereby the entire population of 142 teachers were examined using self-administered questionnaires. The findings indicated that the majority of respondents were male (86%) compared to female (14%). (59.1%) were Bachelor's degree holders, Diploma holders were (22.5%) and Certificate holders (18.3%). Experienced teachers ranged between 6–10 years of teaching experience. The level of students' achievement was low but fair in 2010, with the range mean of (2.5), while in 2011 it still decreased with the range mean of (2.3). Therefore, the negative teachers' attitudes affected students' achievement since the overall teachers' attitude was rated fair, considering (mean = 2.2), which is equivalent to "Disagree" on the Likert scale. The findings also revealed a significant correlation between teachers' attitude and students' achievement, even though the strength of the relationship is negligible, with a sig. value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.01. It was recommended that the Ministry of Education should support private schools financially. School managers should also respond to motivation problems by increasing benefits and improving working conditions (Donnelly <i>et al.</i>, 1995).</p> <p>Keywords: Teachers' Attitude, Students' Performance, Private Schools, Secondary Schools.</p>

Introduction

The Rwandan education system originates from the arrival of missionaries from Europe at the beginning of the twentieth century, who in 1900 established the first formal school at Nyanza (Kareba *et al.*, 2017). Education was controlled by these Christian missionaries, whereby the main subjects were religious studies, reading and writing of European languages, as well as arithmetic (REB, 2020). From 1962, after independence, the education system in Rwanda underwent changes through its history, and this education system was disturbed due to conflicts. Women and men received different education, based on their responsibilities (Wikipedia Contributors, 2026).

Education was informal and delivered largely through the family. Training was also delivered through "amatorero" training schools. These courses included military and war skills, iron smith and foundry, poetry, and basket making. In the colonial days, education developed because of the initiatives of Christian missionaries, whereby education was available to a small elite group, and another group of Rwandans remained illiterate or poorly educated (Gedron, 2000). After independence, the number of teachers who were qualified in secondary schools were only 36% and 33% for lower and upper secondary, respectively. This means that Rwanda was not able to produce a highly skilled workforce, especially when considering the large proportion of teachers who were not qualified to teach secondary school pupils. Most of the teachers felt that

they have been poorly paid. Most secondary school teachers decided to attend different schools as students in order to get higher qualifications outside the teaching domain. This shows that the incentive for further education is low, and there are other jobs that have a higher benefit as compared to teaching in Rwanda. Overall, the lack of quality in the education system, such as the standards of teachers, lack of facilities, and resources, makes schooling unattractive (UNICEF, 2004). Since a long time ago, a teacher has undergone many stresses, whereby he served at the same time as the instructor, a disciplinarian, and an employee (Schaefer, 2003).

Salary is an important source of motivation and a stimulating factor in attracting and retaining highly trained and qualified teachers, which in turn enhances quality education, and needs to be carefully addressed in case a country aims at achieving ambitious goals like those of Rwanda (Habyarimana, 2022). Consequently, this did not spare the educational sector in Rwanda, which faces many problems, whereby teachers undergo inadequate payment, sometimes according to their level of studies. This started a long time ago, where, in order to have adequate education, some parents started their own private schools and hired teachers who would fulfill their intentions. However, while government-aided public schools are sponsored by the government, private schools depend on the number of students they have and the tuition they pay for functioning. From this, in many private schools, teachers' salaries are not given on time, depending on how students pay their school fees.

Three factors lead students to attend private secondary schools:

- 1) A student may not have the chance of going to the upper level in a public school after sitting for the National Examination.
- 2) He/she may have passed the National Examination and not be able to attend a school which is far from his/her home, and finally, sometimes parents choose private schools which are not far from their home.
- 3) According to some parents, private schools provide better quality education than public schools (NCDC 6-year plan, 2004–2009).

Little is known about whether teachers' attitudes have so far influenced students' achievements in Rubavu District. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to assess if teachers' attitudes have so far contributed to students' achievement in Rubavu District, since some researchers only investigated certain variables that have effects on students' achievement, such as "Effects of domestic violence on learning effectiveness" (Sikubwabo, 2021), but have not considered the role of teachers' attitudes on students' performance/effectiveness. However, this research aimed to fill this gap by investigating whether there is any correlation between teachers' attitudes and students' achievement in private schools located in Rubavu District. In addition to this, another research still carried out by Ndayisaba and Sikubwabo (2022), "School feeding and students' performance," neither mentioned any role that may have been played by teachers in boosting students' achievement, nor provided recommendations to education managers on how to motivate or enhance teachers' well-being. Furthermore, only a few studies have investigated the contribution of school feeding programs on students' discipline in secondary schools of Rwanda (Munyantore *et al.*, 2024), School feeding program implementation and students' discipline in Twelve Years Basic Education in Rwanda (Laurence and Andola, 2003), Effects of school feeding program on pupils' enrolment, attendance, and performance in Northern Region of Nigeria (Bulus Barnabas, Miroslava Bavorova, Mustapha Yakubu Madaki). However, no study to date has examined the issue of teachers' attitudes and its relationship with students' achievement, particularly in private secondary schools located in Rubavu District, and the research findings revealed that not only school feeding or other variables above-mentioned have direct effects on students' academic performance, but also teachers' attitudes influence the extent to which students will academically perform.

This study makes several contributions: First of all, it is the first one that was conducted in order to assess the relationship between teachers' attitudes and students' achievement in Rwanda, especially in Rubavu District. Second, by distributing questionnaires to teachers, the research provided a better understanding of teachers' viewpoints regarding their school choices, as well as their teaching career. Finally, by revealing a strong influence of teachers' attitudes on students' achievement, this paper opens doors for future research, which can investigate deeply school facilities and students' performance in Rubavu District or other districts of Rwanda, or school mapping and students' academic performance.

It is therefore with this regard that the researcher wished to carry out this study to assess if teachers' attitudes have so far contributed to students' achievement in private schools located in Rubavu District in Rwanda, at the same time by bridging the above-mentioned research gaps.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers' attitudes and students' achievement are a big challenge, because students' performance, whether we like it or not, is usually the result of teachers' efforts during the teaching-learning process. The possible causes of students' poor performance could be the result of teachers' poor motivation, inefficient salary, poor accommodation, and generally poor working conditions. This has made some teachers decide to run their own businesses, such as farming, being employed at two different institutions, and moreover, some are leaders in local government, whereby they are sometimes needed to attend different meetings regardless of their teaching timetable (TSC Report, 2010).

The teaching profession is feeling pressure in the following three areas:

- 1) The amount of formal schooling required for teaching remains high, and now the public has begun to call for new competency examinations for teachers.
- 2) Teachers' salaries are lower than those of many professionals and skilled workers.
- 3) The overall prestige of the teaching profession has declined. Many teachers have become disappointed and frustrated and have left the educational world for other professions, and those who still remain in education seem not to do their work well, hence students' poor achievement (TSC Report, 2010).

Therefore, the study was to find out if there is any relationship between the type of teachers' attitudes and the level of students' achievement in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District.

Research Questions and Hypothesis

Research questions are formulated requests for information that define the problem to be studied, set boundaries for information collection, and outline the objectives of the investigation. They inquire about the relationship among variables that the investigator seeks to know (Creswell, 2014). On the other hand, research hypotheses are predictions the researcher makes about the expected relationship among variables. The researcher draws inferences about the population from a study sample (Creswell, 2014).

This research is guided by the following research questions:

- i) What are the demographic characteristics of the respondents in terms of age, gender, qualification, working experience, and salary level in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District?
- ii) What is the degree of teachers' attitudes in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District?
- iii) What is the level of students' performance in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District?
- iv) Is there any relationship between teachers' attitude and students' achievement in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District?

The research hypothesis is "There is no significant relationship between teachers' attitudes and students' achievement in selected private secondary schools located in Rubavu District, Rwanda."

Review of Related Literature

Attitudes are evaluations of people, objects, or ideas. They are important because they usually determine what we do, our choices, and these attitudes stem from our genes (Aronson *et al.*, 2002). Attitude is a learned predisposition to respond in a favorable or unfavorable manner to a particular person, object, or idea (Feldman, 1995).

Each attitude serves at least one of three functions:

- i) The Heuristic/The Instrumental Function:** Through this, we develop favorable attitudes toward objects that aid or reward us, and unfavorable attitudes towards objects that punish us. Once they are developed, attitudes provide a simple and efficient means of evaluating objects.
- ii) Schematic/Knowledge Function:** They provide us with a meaningful environment and guide behaviour.
- iii) Self and Maintained Self-Worth:** The third defines both the self and maintains self-worth. Some attitudes symbolize a person's identification with or membership in a particular group or subculture (Michener and DeLamater, 1999).

It was found that teachers possess few of the power resources found in other professions. The studies revealed that they also lack the economic sanctions found in few professions; their career circuits are relatively undeveloped, and their formal and legal status within the school system is weak (Baldrige and Deal, 1975).

Teachers' Commitment

According to the American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language, commitment is the state of being bound emotionally or intellectually to a course of action or to another person or persons: a deep commitment to liberal policies; a profound commitment to the family (American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language, 2011).

Supervision

A teacher does his/her teaching practice in schools and needs to be stimulated, motivated, supported, guided, etc. That process is called supervision. In teacher education, we normally see two supervisors: the school supervisor, who is mostly an experienced teacher in the school where the student teachers do his/her practice, and the institutional supervisor. Teacher education institutions have their own system to supervise student teachers during their practice. When teachers do their practice in several different countries, they need to be supervised in all places in a way that is consistent for them (Sergiovanni and Starratt, 2002).

The model of teacher supervision is familiar in the following aspects:

- i) The principal sits in the back of the classroom while the lesson is going on.
- ii) The teacher prepares a lesson beforehand.
- iii) The provision of a write-up by the principal.
- iv) Making some suggestions.
- v) Moving to the next teacher (Dudney, 2002).

Job Security

Job security is the probability that an individual will keep his or her job; a job with a high level of job security is such that a person with the job would have a small chance of becoming unemployed. Job security is dependent on the economy, prevailing business conditions, and the individual's personal skills. It has been found that people have more job security in times of economic expansion and less in times of a recession (Wikipedia Contributors, 2025).

Also, some laws bolster job security by making it illegal to fire employees for certain reasons. The unemployment rate is a good indicator of job security and the state of the economy and is tracked by economists, government officials, and banks. Typically, government jobs and jobs in education, healthcare, and law enforcement are considered very secure, while private sector jobs are generally believed to offer lower job security and it usually varies by industry, location, occupation and other factors (Wikipedia Contributors, 2025).

Students' Discipline

Students' discipline means setting clear rules which are consistent in order to create a respectful learning environment. It also defines rules and norms to be followed, as well as accepted behaviors at school (Kumari, 2025). There are several factors that may lead to the breakdown of discipline, such as poverty, overcrowding, lack of recreational facilities, easy access to the school compound, intolerance, unemployment, violence, lack of school democracy, generation gap, and influence of media, lack of role models, home failure, as well as the lack of effective communication (Lewis, 2001). Students, as well as teachers, are involved together with the school manager in maintaining discipline at school (Nakuya, 2021).

Students' Achievement

Students' achievement is defined as the measurable outcomes that are assessed through standardized tests (OECD, 2023). On the other hand, achievement is both academic and the development of skills for lifelong learning. It is the ability of a student to support himself or herself in society after completing the educational process (National Research Council, 2012). The Government of Rwanda started the policy of Nine Years Basic Education (9YBE) in 2009 in order to promote students' achievement, whereby students gain nine years of free education. From the year 2011, the Government of Rwanda adopted another policy of Twelve Years Basic Education with the same purpose (Ministry of Education, 2012).

Theoretical Perspectives

This study on teachers' attitudes and students' achievement in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District was based on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory of Motivation (1959), which is based on the assumption that motivator and hygienic factors are similar for all employees. Herzberg's two-factor theory suggests that there are two factors that influence job satisfaction, namely hygiene and motivator factors. While motivators

lead to higher motivation and satisfaction at the workplace, such as achievement, as well as recognition, hygiene factors, on the other hand, such as salaries as well as working conditions, prevent dissatisfaction; however, they do not necessarily motivate workers (Nickerson, 2025).

Motivator Factors

These are aspects of job content and organizational context that create positive feelings among employees. Challenges of the work itself, responsibility, recognition, achievement, advancement, and growth are motivator factors. These factors determine whether a job is exciting and rewarding, as well as resulting in employees who feel excited and committed to their work (Slocum *et al.*, 2002).

Hygienic Factors

Hygienic factors are the non-task characteristics of the work environment, and the organizational context, that create dissatisfaction. They include compensation, level of responsibility, working conditions, company policies, supervision, coworkers, salary, formal status, and job security. The absence of dissatisfaction is a vital but not sufficient condition to motivate employees at the workplace; however, they help create a work setting that makes it possible to motivate employees (Hellriegel *et al.*, 2002). According to Bamisaiye (1983), it is required to pay money in order to attract, retain, and develop the staff for effective functioning of the school. Herzberg’s two-factor theory of motivation states that when hygiene needs are not met, workers are dissatisfied, and when hygiene needs are met, workers are not dissatisfied (Gareth and George, 2003). This theory is important to the study because it brings out the factors that affect teachers’ attitudes to their work, which, when met, can enable teachers to perform their work efficiently, therefore achieving the school goals, especially high students’ achievement.

Methodology

The design of this study is a descriptive survey, and the strategy adopted is descriptive correlation. The researcher correlated teachers’ attitudes and students’ achievement.

Research Population

The study was carried out in all 14 private secondary schools in Rubavu District, and the target population was all 142 respondents, which comprised the teaching staff of the selected private secondary schools located in Rubavu District.

Sample Size

The study used the total sampling method to determine respondents, whereby all 142 teachers were selected, whereby 122 were male and 20 were female. Table 1 determines the sample size by convenience method, where the sample is determined at the discretion of the researcher.

Table 1. Population and sample size.

Schools	Target population		Sample size	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
School A	7	–	7	–
School B	9	1	9	1
School C	8	2	8	2
School D	9	2	9	2
School E	10	1	10	1
School F	6	2	6	2
School G	8	2	8	2
School H	10	2	10	2
School I	10	2	10	2
School J	10	1	10	1
School K	7	–	7	–
School L	10	2	10	2
School M	8	1	8	1
School N	10	2	10	2
Total	122	20	122	20
Grand total	142		142	

Source: Primary data (2012).

According to the table above, Rubavu District was comprised of 14 private secondary schools with 142 teachers, whereby 122 teachers were male, while only 20 were female.

Sampling Procedure

The researcher used the total sampling method, which is a type of purposive sampling method that considers the entire and specific population rather than representatives (<https://dissertation.laerd.com/total-population-sampling.php>).

Research Instruments

The researcher, in order to collect information from respondents, used the following research instruments:

i) Face Sheet: This helped the researcher to gather data on respondents' profile characteristics, such as age, gender, educational qualification, teachers' experience, and the level of their salary.

ii) Researcher-Devised Questionnaires: These helped determine the degree of teachers' attitudes. This consists of options referring to supervision, motivation, and teachers' commitment, discipline, and job satisfaction.

The response mode and scoring were as follows: Strongly agree (4); Agree (3); Disagree (2); Strongly disagree (1).

Data Analysis

The frequency and percentage distribution were used to determine the demographic characteristics of the respondents. For students' performance, the mean was used, whereas for the level of teachers' attitudes, the mean and rank were used, and Pearson's linear correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between teachers' attitude and the level of students' achievement.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of the study are presented as follows:

Research Question 1

Research Question 1 was formulated as follows: "What are the demographic characteristics of the respondents in terms of age, gender, qualification, working experience, and salary level in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District?" The results were presented according to the responses provided by respondents on their profile, as presented in the following table.

Table 2. Profile of respondents.

Main category	Subcategory	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	122	86.0
	Female	20	14.0
	Total	142	100
Age (years)	20-30	28	19.7
	31-39	72	50.7
	40-49	42	29.6
	Total	142	100
Level of education	Certificate	26	18.3
	Diploma	32	22.5
	Bachelor	84	59.2
	Total	142	100
Teaching experience	1-5 years	52	36.6
	6-10 years	70	49.3
	11 years and above	20	14.1
	Total	142	100
Salary level (RWF)	Low (25,000-40,000)	26	18.3
	Average (45,000-90,000)	32	22.5
	High (\geq 100,000)	84	59.2
	Total	142	100

Source: Primary data (2012).

From Table 2, findings showed that the majority of the respondents were male (81%), while the minority were females (19%). However, the difference in gender participation in the study was very big. This implies that most of the private secondary schools prefer to employ males than females. Regarding age, findings revealed that the majority of the respondents were of the age range 31–39 (47%), while the minority were of the age bracket of 40–49 (24%). The findings showed that the majority of teachers were youths. In relation to education level, the majority of teachers were Bachelor’s degree holders (75%), followed by Diploma holders (33%), while (10%) were certificate holders. The results show that most of the respondents who participated in the study had a university level of education, while the remaining portion had attained Diploma and certificate level of education.

The findings show that the respondents who participated in the study were literate and were able to understand the questions presented to them about the study topic. Regarding work experience, respondents who had served for a period of 1–5 years were (28%), (67%) of the respondents had served for a period of 6–10 years, while (05%) had served for a period of 11 years and above in their teaching career. This implies that the study endeavored to involve respondents who had stayed in the teaching career for a long time and were knowledgeable about the issues that the study sought. The salary level of the majority of teachers of private secondary schools in Rubavu District, Rwanda, was rated high, whereby 59.1% of teachers get a salary which varies from 100,000 RWF and above. This is justified by the fact that the majority of teachers were Bachelor’s degree holders. 22.5% of the private secondary teachers in the area of study get an average salary ranging between 45,000–90,000 RWF. These teachers are Diploma holders, whereas 18.3% of them who are certificate holders get a low salary ranging between 25,000–40,000 RWF.

Research Question 2

Research Question 2 was formulated as follows: “What is the degree of teachers’ attitudes in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District?”

To measure this, respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agree or disagree with each of the questions by identifying the numbers that described their perception. All responses on teachers’ attitudes were put on a Likert scale using four (4) points ranging from 1–4: 4 = Strongly agree, 3 = Agree, 2 = Disagree, 1 = Strongly disagree. Their responses were analyzed and described using the mean and ranked, as summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Teacher’s attitude and motivation.

Degree of teacher’s commitment			
Statement	Mean	Rank	Interpretation
There is interaction with students during the teaching process	3.4	2	Satisfactory
An effective approach to students’ academic problems is giving them more exercises	2.5	7	Fair
Students get feedback after interacting with them	2.2	8	Fair
Students receive homework at the end of every lesson	2.1	9	Fair
The teaching methodology used provides students with the opportunity to develop and build their own understanding	2.0	10	Fair
All teaching periods are covered during working hours	1.8	12	Fair
Permission is asked before absence	1.8	12	Fair
Teachers are always in class on time	1.7	13	Fair
Average mean	2.1	-	Fair
To determine teachers’ motivation			
Salary delay demoralizes teachers	4.0	1	Very satisfactory
Monthly salary in private schools is more attractive than public schools	2.6	6	Satisfactory
Monthly salary motivates teachers	2.6	6	Satisfactory
Salary helps to maintain and enhance professional status	2.5	7	Fair
Teachers are provided with breakfast and lunch	2.2	8	Fair
Teachers are provided with accommodation	1.9	11	Fair
There is time to do other activities after working hours	1.7	13	Fair
Average mean	2.4	-	Fair
Source: Primary data (2012).			

The results in Table 3 indicated that the degree of teachers' commitment in the selected secondary schools was rated fair, considering (average mean = 2.1), which is equivalent to disagree on the Likert scale. This shows that because of different factors which dissatisfy teachers, they do not do their work well. However, it was accepted that interaction is well done between teachers and students, with the mean of 3.4, which is equivalent to agree on the Likert scale. This is because, in whatever circumstances, whenever a teacher is in the classroom, he/she must interact with students in one way or another. On the other hand, the degree of teachers' motivation in the selected secondary schools was rated fair, considering (average mean = 2.4), which is equivalent to disagree on the Likert scale. This may be caused by the fact that most private schools don't regularly pay teachers' salaries due to their dependence on students' tuition. Moreover, the lack of accommodation and other facilities leads to poor motivation. Among the factors which discourage teachers is salary delay, whereby it has a mean of 4, which is equivalent to very satisfactory on the Likert scale. Here, teachers mentioned that when salaries are delayed, they are demoralized, and it becomes very hard to teach effectively.

Table 4. Work satisfaction and school supervision.

Work satisfaction			
Statement	Mean	Rank	Interpretation
Monthly salary satisfies teachers	3.1	3	Satisfactory
Being a teacher is disadvantageous	2.7	5	Satisfactory
All teaching subjects are taken into consideration	2.1	9	Fair
Teaching career was for me the last resort	2.0	10	Fair
The language used in the classroom facilitates students to perform better	1.9	11	Fair
Working conditions are favorable at work	1.9	11	Fair
More time is spent on students for their best achievement	1.8	12	Fair
There are promotions in terms of salary each year	1.6	14	Poor
Average mean	2.0	-	Fair
Schools' supervision			
The headmaster's supervision makes teachers updated	4.0	1	Very satisfactory
There is high supervision at work	3.1	3	Satisfactory
The management style motivates teachers	2.8	4	Satisfactory
After supervision, students result shows that they have understood the lesson	1.9	11	Fair
There is provision of other facilities to teachers to enhance their teaching career	1.6	14	Poor
The Ministry of Education organizes supervisory visits to our school	1.5	15	Poor
Average mean	2.4	-	Fair
Overall mean	2.2	-	Fair
Source: Primary data (2012).			

The results in Table 4 indicated that the degree of work satisfaction in the selected secondary schools was rated fair, considering (average mean = 2), which is equivalent to disagree on the Likert scale. This may be caused by the fact that some of the working conditions are not good, or because of low salaries, whereby some teachers consider teaching as a second option. Despite the fact that the satisfaction with the salary was rated satisfactory, which is equivalent to agree, a big gap is still there between other factors which must be satisfied in order to lead to teachers' satisfaction at their work.

Furthermore, the results on school supervision indicated that the degree of school supervision in the selected secondary schools was rated fair, considering (mean = 2.4), which is equivalent to disagree on the Likert scale. This may be caused by the fact that it is very difficult to supervise or make inspection on workers who are not motivated. Even though some factors were rated very satisfactory, with the mean of 4.0 for the headmasters' supervision, this does not lead to adequate commitment, as it was shown that even after the inspection, the outcome was rated fair. Overall, teachers' attitude in the selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District was rated fair, considering (mean = 2.2), which is equivalent to disagree on the Likert scale. This is because of a lack of motivation, lack of good working conditions, and lack of commitment to their work. However, there are some cases where respondents rated items to be very high. For example, high supervision and interaction with students, which still marks a big gap between them and other factors. These study findings are in

conformity with Herzberg’s hygienic factor theory (1959), which states that the environment and the organizational context that create dissatisfaction, such as working conditions, company policies, supervision, and salary, when they are not met, workers are dissatisfied (Gareth and George, 2003). In the same angle, the findings of this research agree with Ferret and Peak (2000), who stated that employees with a negative attitude look at the downside of the situation, see the worst in others, have a poor self-image, and seem indifferent, fearful, and critical. Also, Woessmann (2001) stated that the availability of instructional materials affects the quality of learning that the school delivers. This work is also in conformity with Gómez-Mejía *et al.*, (2002), who found that the strength to act in a particular way depends on people’s beliefs that their actions will produce outcomes they find valuable and attractive. They also found that employees work harder if they believe their hard work will lead to better appraisals and promotion.

Research Question 3

The research question 3 was formulated as follows: “What is the level of students’ performance in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District?” This is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Students’ level of performance on the national exam, 2010–2011.

Schools	Mean score 2010	Mean score 2011
School A	3.1	3.0
School B	3.2	2.8
School C	3.0	3.2
School D	4.1	3.1
School E	2.3	2.0
School F	2.5	2.1
School G	4.4	3.3
School H	1.8	1.5
School I	2.2	1.6
School J	3.4	2.2
School K	1.2	2.2
School L	1.6	1.8
School M	1.4	1.3
School N	1.2	2.1
Total mean	35.4	32.2
Average mean	2.5	2.3
Source: Primary data (2012).		
Mean range: 3.26–4.00 = Very high (very satisfactory); Mean range: 2.51–3.25 = High (satisfactory); Mean range: 1.76–2.50 = Low (fair); Mean range: 1.00–1.75 = Very low (poor)		

Table 5 shows that in 2010, the performance of students was greater than that of 2011. Whereby, in 2010, the total mean score was at 35.9, with an average mean of 2.5, which is rated to be low (fair). In 2011, the findings further indicate a decline in performance, where the total mean score was at 32.2, with an average mean of 2.3, which is also rated to be low (fair). The possible cause of this decline is because of poor working conditions at the workplace and low payments, which demoralized teachers and hence low student performance. This may also have been caused by the fact that during 2011, the Ministry of Education added new subjects in the National Exams which were not formally done before, hence not being well prepared from the previous years.

Research Question 4

The research question 4 was formulated as follows: “Is there any relationship between the nature of teachers’ attitude and the level of students’ achievement in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District?” For which it was hypothesized that the two variables are not significantly related. To test this hypothesis, Pearson’s Linear Correlation Coefficient (PLCC) was used. The summary of the R-value and sig. value of those variables is presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Relationship between teachers’ attitude and students’ achievement.

Variable correlated	r-value	Sig. value	Interpretation	Decision on H ₀
Teachers’ attitude vs. students’ achievement	0.01	0.000	Positive and significant	Rejected
Source: Primary data (2012).				

Table 6 indicates that the correlation between teachers' attitude and students' achievement was positive and significant, even though the relationship is negligible ($r = 0.01$, $\text{sig.} = 0.000$), which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis that teachers' attitude does not have a significant effect on students' achievement. This means that well-motivated teachers will always have a positive attitude towards their teaching career, which leads to high commitment towards work and hence influences better performance of students.

These findings are in conformity with Neuhaus, citing Zajda (2003), whose findings, based on the expectancy theory of motivation, found that an individual's behavior was motivated by anticipated results or consequences, and the intensity of their work was driven by the perception that their effort would lead to the desired outcome, or in other words, employees are motivated if they believe performance will lead to desired rewards (Neuhaus, 2024). This implies that if teachers have no expectancy on the outcome of what they may have done which could motivate them, it would lead to the development of a negative attitude towards their work, which, as it is shown by the results of this work, has a negative impact on students' achievement.

In his research on the relationship between teachers' attitudes and students' academic achievement in mathematics in some selected senior secondary schools in Southern Nigeria, Yara (2009) found that there was a positive attitude of teachers towards the teaching of mathematics in secondary schools, in spite of the shortcomings that have bedeviled the teaching profession, and particularly in the teaching of mathematics. Therefore, this can lead to the conclusion that when teachers are motivated and have developed positive attitudes toward their teaching job, this will lead to positive students' academic achievement (Yara, 2009).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to test the null hypothesis which states that there is no relationship between teachers' attitudes and students' achievement in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District, Rwanda. It was confirmed that a positive relationship exists between the two variables. The findings of this study also agreed with Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation (1959), on which this study was based, which states that motivators and hygienic factors determine satisfaction or dissatisfaction of a worker. This means that dissatisfied teachers can develop negative attitudes, hence this affects students' achievement.

Furthermore, the first students' results of 2010 show that students had a low average mean, and the following year it declined, with the average mean of 2.3. This implies that teachers developed a negative attitude and were not committed well to their work, since there was no improvement. Therefore, this study tested the hypothesis and found that there is a very significant relationship between teachers' attitude and students' achievement in selected private secondary schools in Rubavu District, Rwanda.

All in all, the study generated data which led to all the findings about the correlation between teachers' attitude and students' achievement. This means that if teachers develop a positive attitude, students can perform better. But if teachers develop a negative attitude, students' performance will decline, as it was revealed by this study.

Recommendations

The findings of the study led the researcher to give the following recommendations:

- 1) The Government of Rwanda, through the Ministry of Education, should give support to private secondary schools, since it is known that either private or public schools all have the objectives of educating Rwandese children. Therefore, quality education concerns all schools regardless of their status. On the other hand, private schools have to increase the number of female teachers, because they can also contribute to the promotion of education as males can.
- 2) In addition, it is recommended that private schools should do their best to treat their teachers well, in terms of regular salary promotion and providing accommodation, in order to avoid absenteeism, which eventually affects students' achievement. The Government of Rwanda, through the Ministry of Education, should organize permanent seminars to train teachers and keep them updated.

Declarations

Acknowledgements: The author gratefully acknowledges the management of Kigali Independent University (ULK), especially the President and Founder, Professor Dr. Rwigamba Balinda, for his leadership, invaluable hard work, commitment, as well as determination. The researcher acknowledges that this work would not have been accomplished without his generous support. The author is also thankful to the Deputy Vice-Chancellor Academic of Kigali Independent University–Gisenyi Campus, Lecturer Hagumimana Frank; the

Director of Administration and Finance, Mr. Karara Alexis; all Heads of Departments; as well as the entire staff of ULK for their invaluable encouragement and guidance throughout the research process.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Use Statement: AI tools were not used in the design of the study, data collection, data analysis, or interpretation of the findings. The author takes full responsibility for the originality, accuracy, and integrity of the content presented in this paper.

Author Contribution: The author confirms responsibilities for the study manuscript, design, data collection, conception, as well as the analysis and interpretation of results.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

Consent to Publish: The author agrees to publish this paper in International Journal of Recent Innovation in Academic Research.

Data Availability Statement: Data about respondents' profiles are confidential and can only be accessed by the author of this paper. Other data contained in this paper can be accessed by the public. The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the author upon reasonable request.

Funding: The author did not receive any external funding to publish this paper.

Informed Consent: All respondents signed the informed consent form and participated voluntarily.

Research Content: The author declares that this research manuscript is original and has not been published elsewhere.

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Citation: Salongo Muyobokey. 2026. Teachers Attitude and Students' Achievement in Selected Private Secondary Schools in Rubavu District, Rwanda. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 10(1): 74-85.

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